

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract: The role of the digital economy in today's rapidly developing information age is invaluable. In order to see Uzbekistan among the developed countries, it is necessary to develop the digital economy and eliminate existing problems. Effective use of new opportunities and wider promotion of automation remains one of the topical topics of today.

Key words: digital economy, economy, information, information communication, information technologies, automation, digitization.

The development of the digital economy has many advantages for the country and humanity. For example, the development of the information and communication sectors creates a great opportunity to save time, which is the most valuable human resource, and to use it effectively and rationally. If we buy an electronic version of a book instead of a paper copy, we will use our precious time effectively. Through the development of information and communication technologies, we will save not only our time, but also our money. We do not need to stand in queues for hours or go to banks to make utility payments, we will be able to make reliable payments anywhere at any time. This process will also be very useful for our women with limited opportunities or young children. In addition to doing their household chores, they also have the opportunity to easily buy necessary or household products from online stores. In addition, digital technology can be effectively used in education, it will be possible to be aware of the student's mastery level, the grades he receives in subjects, the teacher and the student's attendance and achievements in classes.

Even in industrial enterprises, the organization of digital technologies gives a significant impetus to work efficiency. In addition to cost savings, the widespread use of digitization will improve the quality and accuracy of the process, as well as the quality management process.

The development of the digital economy in a country, which is directly related to the level of development of information and communication technologies (ICT), is usually evaluated by various indicators. These indicators include: the share of the digital economy in the GDP, the volume of investments in the field of ICT, the speed of the Internet, its coverage of the territory of the country and its ease of

use for the population, the level of development of e-commerce. , the share of public services in the electronic government system, provision of organizations with ICT specialists, etc. In addition, indicators evaluating the development of information technologies are also important.

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As we can see, the level of development of electronic government in Uzbekistan is not low, but not high either. It is no exaggeration to say that the founders of the digital economy were, in a sense, our ancestors. The great mathematician Muhammad Khorezmi laid the unique foundation stone of the digital economy 1200 years ago by creating a modern decimal calculation system and using an algorithmic, i.e., systematic approach to solving problems. This made it possible to perform calculations faster not only in science and education, but also in everyday life, especially in the economy. At the moment, there are sufficient opportunities and conditions for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, but the development stage is very slow. In order to eliminate this, a number of reforms are being implemented in our country. As the President of our country, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, stated in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020: "In order to achieve progress, it is necessary and necessary for us to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension. After all, today information technology is deeply penetrating all areas of the world"

In conclusion, it should be noted that the digital economy is developing in Uzbekistan as well as in the countries of the world. After the application of information technology in our life today, many opportunities are created for ordinary people. Nowadays, without leaving home, we can order many products and food and have them delivered to our home. But it should be noted that the digital economy in Uzbekistan is developing several times slower than the potential of Uzbekistan. That is, there is an opportunity, the necessary resources are available, but the development is very slow. As a reason for this, a number of obstacles to the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan can be pointed out: monopolies in many areas, low internet speed and poor quality, legislation in the field of information technology is behind the times, extremely low computer literacy among citizens, lack of transparency of legislation, lack of information technology specialists or we can attribute them to leaving to other countries, information culture, information hygiene is low, information technology security is not good, there are few specialists who understand the field in management bodies or (in some cases) they are not there at all, and similar situations.

If the above-mentioned problems are solved gradually, systematically, based on world experience, Uzbekistan can easily become one of the countries with a developed digital economy.

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